

A Proustian Approach to the Study of Politics

Nathan J. Brown

Nathan J. Brown is Professor of Political Science and International Affairs and the Assistant Dean of Graduate Studies at the Elliot School of International Affairs at The George Washington University (GWU).

Editors' Note: Last year, Nathan Brown received the 2025 Michael E. Brown Research Prize, the foremost research award at GWU's Elliot School of International Affairs. A lightly edited version of Brown's address on September 24, 2025, follows below. Brown, as many of our readers know, is a leading scholar of Middle East politics, judicial and constitutional orders, and – the subject of his current book manuscript, which he draws on in his address below – the relationship between religion and state. In his speech, Brown reflects on his own work and what he identifies as an area of promising overlap in both social and area studies: to “help people see what each other sees.” In many ways, this is a speech about boundaries and boundary-crossing – from one's subjective position to that of another, and from the descriptive to the normative. Toward the end of his remarks, Brown situates his own approach – to boundaries and to their transgression – in the (then) current context of Israel's war on Gaza, the discourse in US policy circles, and the cycles of activism and repression on our college campuses. Because these remarks were delivered orally, we have included a minimal number of academic references for readability.

It's an honor to receive an award named for my former dean, Michael Brown. Let me first assure you that there is no nepotism—I have traced my ancestry back some generations and can identify every Brown I am related to—and Michael is not one of them. So that makes it even more special to bear his name.

But at a time when the benefits of scholarly research are increasingly questioned; when analysis of international affairs seems as deeply polarized as every other subject, from employment statistics to the weather; when “professor” is not always a term of respect, is recognition by one's colleagues still such an honor? The current moment has made me reflect a bit more personally on why I do what I do. And I will use this opportunity to share some of those reflections with you.

I will begin my personal reflections first, *pretentiously*, by quoting Marcel Proust. I will proceed second, *pedantically*, by lecturing you on how Proust has been misinterpreted, then, in turn, *pompously*, by comparing my work to Proust's sense of aesthetic mission. But most of my talk will then proceed *prosaically* (with a word about *punctuation*) by trying to explain what I do—which has less to do with discovering truth and more to do with helping people understand each other when they see the truth so differently. That will be the bulk of my remarks. But I will then inject some *political* thoughts about what *I* see as truth. I will conclude *practically* with some thoughts about how to present truth when it can be seen as provocative.

So on to my pretentious beginning, which is Proustian—literally.

When I was twenty-two years old and just about to begin a doctoral program, my best friend from high school told me that the best way to take advantage of the privilege of being human was to read (or reread) a volume of Proust every year. I was especially eager to retain my humanity while completing a PhD, so I began. “For a long time I used to go to bed early,” Proust began slowly.¹ But I was even more slow. I took my comprehensives, conducted field work, and wrote up my dissertation—and was still just starting the second volume. I soldiered on as I became an assistant, an associate, and then a full professor. I became a parent and then a grandparent. I carried Proust to different cities and countries and continents. In 2024, almost four and a half decades after reading about Proust’s going to bed, I finally finished all seven volumes; I did so, I am proud to say, before becoming professor emeritus. So I failed the timeline, but the undertaking still did me some good. And in the process I came across a particular passage in volume 5 that I had heard before, since it is frequently quoted:

The only true voyage of discovery, the only fountain of Eternal Youth, would be not to visit strange lands but to possess other eyes, to behold the universe through the eyes of another, of a hundred others, to behold the hundred universes that each of them beholds, that each of them is.

A more extended version of that passage is frequently cited to explain the virtues of international travel. I even found some of its words emblazoned on the wall of a lounge in Charles de Gaulle Airport.

But here is where I move from the *preten-*

tious to the *pedantic*, since it is clear from the passage that it has nothing to do with traveling—just the opposite. Flying to strange lands with the senses we already have does us no good since we still see with our old eyes. We need to see things through the eyes of others.

And that brings me quickly to the *pompous*, where I claim to understand Proust better than the decorators of the Paris airport. What Proust actually suggested was that there were certain uniquely gifted artists whose aesthetic senses allowed them to see things none of us would otherwise be aware of and then to make those worlds accessible to us.

So am I such an artist?

Heavens no; here my pomposity tapers off. I do not see things others cannot. Instead, I try to help people see each other—or to help people see what each other sees. So here I turn from the *pompous* to the *prosaic* and to punctuation to focus in the body of my remarks.

I see much of my job as helping people understand each other. And my main tool is a punctuation mark—the semicolon, that allows us to keep two thoughts in mind, linking them while also treating them separately and sequentially. I use the semicolon to pause between understanding and judgment.

The subject matter of the social sciences is much older than the current range of academic disciplines. People interact, govern, trade, communicate, move, cooperate, fight, argue, deliberate, dominate, vote, and make rules—and they started doing so long before

¹ This, and subsequent references to Proust, come from his seven-volume magnum opus, *À la recherche du temps perdu* (In Search of Lost Time), published between 1913 and 1927, and for which many English language translations are available.

a few people decided to devise ways of understanding the patterns by which they do so. Many—but not all—of those within social science disciplines have felt it helpful to draw a border between understanding and judgment; between the empirical and the normative; between explanation and prescription. Many seek to understand the world as it is, not judge it for what it fails to be.

But not all. The drawing of a line between empirical and normative scholarship is controversial, precisely because it seems to push good and evil beyond the margin. Worse, it can push them underground, where they operate fully but out of conscious view.

I find it can be very useful to distinguish what is from what ought to be—and I therefore try to present many of my understandings without judgment. But I also insist on the benefit of crossing over that border between them. That is where a semicolon can be useful, especially in a world in which people's experiences, expectations, and presumptions are so different. It can pay to pause to understand different points of view before proceeding to prescription, policy, or practice. In a world in which people with such diverse lives come into increasing contact, liberal use of a semicolon makes managing of difference, learning, and communication much easier.²

And there is a policy payoff as well—when we proceed this way, we can speak not truth to power but truths; we can try to induce those who wield power to understand that the world as they see it is not the world as many others experience it.

And here let me move beyond punctuation to

method. I think those who approach scholarship like me work to make the familiar appear unfamiliar and to render the unfamiliar more familiar.

In the first part of this method, we work to complicate what we take for granted; to help us understand that what we see around is not always natural or inevitable; to make us less likely to take what we know as the only way to do or see things. We can make the familiar appear a bit...odd.

And the second thing we can do—making the unfamiliar familiar—prevents us from recoiling from anything that we initially see as exotic or anomalous.

Moving within and across cultures, “area studies” as an enterprise often works to explain phenomena by translating what is unfamiliar into familiar terms. Instead of treating the unfamiliar as alien, it might use analogy or metaphor to make it more familiar.

The methods I describe are designed not to eliminate complexity and difference. They help us cope with them and help overcome barriers to understanding. They allow us to understand our differences as historically contingent rather than essential.

Let me explain that in terms of my current work on religion and state. I find too much writing that juxtaposes a secular West against a religious Middle East. And many that trace that distinction to distant historical origins: seventh-century Mecca or seventeenth-century Westphalia.

Such an approach is clearly taken in many

² And I practice what I preach, using the semicolon in my writing, silently but unmistakably in my speech and now deploying it as a metaphor in [my newly launched podcast series](#), “Semicolons and Teardrops in the Middle East”.

attempts to understand the history of higher education. In a post-Westphalian West, and in a United States with a wall of separation between church and state, we see universities that relegate religion to the private sphere; in the Middle East, where Islam knows no separation between religion and state, we see religious universities, like Egypt's al-Azhar, or state universities that still teach shari'a and other religious subjects.

This division may seem clear, but it is not quite right. Let me start by making clear that Western universities do not fit this familiar pattern—or any pattern—so easily. Consider that state universities in the real German state of Westphalia teach Catholic and Protestant theology under the supervision of religious authorities. That's not unusual in Europe—but it's not universal either. French universities are barred from teaching theology—except in Alsace.

Closer to home, we see the country's first institution of higher education, Harvard, guaranteed its privileges because, according to a clause of the Massachusetts constitution in effect today, “the encouragement of arts and sciences, and all good literature, tends to the honor of God [and] the advantage of the Christian religion,” (Massachusetts Constitution chap. 5, § 1, art. 1). The University of Michigan was founded to give effect to a treaty obligation of the United States government to provide support for a Catholic college to the Ottawa, Chippewa, and Potawatomy peoples.³ Our own George Washington University was founded to educate Baptist clergy and provide missionaries to Asia and the American West, and—closer to home—to prevent the population of federal offices by Catholics educated at nearby Georgetown.⁴

These familiar institutions in Westphalia and Washington DC, Alsace and Paris, are more varied and strange than we realize.

American universities look a bit odd in global terms in a manner we often overlook. There are few other systems of higher education that have defined “religion” as a generic subject and channeled that subject into something that looks like an academic discipline; we have rounded up many of the specialists and put them in a department. But we have done so only fairly recently.

What explains these patterns if they do not fit into a secular West versus religious rest? Across the globe, as extensive and intensive state apparatuses were built—generally in the nineteenth and the first half of the twentieth centuries—they oversaw the emergence of formalized structures for mass elementary and secondary education. In fact, they invented those stages. And they clearly defined and demarcated post-secondary stages in institutions that combined education, scientific and scholarly research. And as this formalized and official educational apparatus arose, those building them often encountered structures, practices, and intellectual traditions that were religious in nature.

That was not a Western pattern; it was a familiar process that took place in Sri Lanka, Mexico, Egypt, and the United States of America at roughly the same time. But if most states built universities, each one handled religion a bit differently—not based on any essential nature of Christianity, Islam, or Westphalia. Instead, basic choices simply reflected society and politics at the time.

In the United States, structures of religion

³ The text of that treaty can be found [here](#).

⁴ This point is addressed in my forthcoming book, *Religion and State*.

and education were shaped by struggles, mostly in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, among Protestants and between Catholics and Protestants. There were conflicts over the education of indigenous peoples, teaching religious texts and doctrine in public schools, and what “nonsectarian” meant. And the struggles played out in various venues, including in federal courts and the Internal Revenue Code.

In Egypt, around the same time, higher education institutions were shaped by a very different set of struggles among Ottoman, Egyptian, and British officials. Some of the issues they grappled with were similar to those that emerged in the United States, and some were different. The outcomes, in both cases, were shaped by the demands of a rapidly expanding bureaucratic state and economic development patterns and trajectories.

In 2023, a public Swiss university advertised for a position in Jewish theology. In addition to scholarly credentials and knowledge of relevant languages, there was one additional requirement: only members of the Catholic Church should apply. The requirement made perfect sense in terms of the way that religion operates within the context of the Swiss state—and is utterly confounding outside its borders.

In this way, what appears to be familiar, a Western-style university, appears far less uniform, inevitable, or even “Western”; non-Western universities appear far more familiar, and not distinctly “non-Western”. And the effects of decisions, often made for reasons long forgotten, continue to this day.

Seen this way, our task in the social sciences is fourfold—and the first three involve understanding. First, we explore the world(s)

that exist within our assumed borders—and the various ways those living within these borders experience, enforce, and push against them. But second, we seek to explore the lives of those on the opposite sides of these borders. We seek to communicate not only within one world but to translate between these worlds.

Why? That is the third task: to understand how those differences shape outcomes—and we do so, or at least I do so, in the hope that it will make us less likely to hurt each other. The goal is not agreement; a world in which everyone agreed, devoid of difference, disagreement, or borders, would be a world without politics, one without growth or learning, one of monotonous uniformity. A world in which people only enforce borders and never cross them, in which deviations from the familiar are viewed as crimes against nature, would be violent and confining. We explore disagreement and float above borders so that we may understand each other through our differences.

And that sounds so...positive. And nice. But sometimes we have to say things that might be a bit less nice. What I have discussed so far is a combination of odd curiosities and paths laid down in the past; the Brown award is to be for “policy-relevant understanding of important global issues.” We do not only explore the past; we make judgments about the present. And when we do so, we sometimes address not only what is and why but also what we think should be done—and that is the fourth task.

So now I move from the *prosaic* to the *political*, and this will bring me to the far side of the semicolon between understanding and judgment. While it can be harmful to rush to judgment, we do have to meander over there

eventually; to fail to do so would be to keep our minds so open that our brains would fall out.

How and when to do so has been a deeply divisive question in the academy in recent years, and none more so than in the set of issues I have focused on intermittently for three decades, related to Israel and Palestine. Since October 7, 2023, the issues that have never been easy to discuss seem to have become impossible to discuss.

In general, my own approach when dealing with such a challenge has been to linger on the “understanding” side of the semicolon and not rush to the “judgment” side. And while that suddenly became harder two years ago, it was also a time when it was more important than ever to understand why people were doing what they were doing—even if they were doing some awful things. Again, that did not mean avoiding any normative judgments; it just meant not leading with them.

So when I spoke as a scholar, I tried several things. I attempted to measure my words by assuming my audience did not agree with me. I tried to speak in paragraphs—not to render my answers tedious, but to give myself space to offer analysis and understanding of various points of view. I inclined toward understatement on most occasions—to lead with strong language can leave an audience feel shouted at. In an environment in which people are being told what to think and even what to feel, a voice that helped them work their way through the issues and the passions seemed more likely to be heard. I worked to avoid personalizing arguments; it was actions and deeds (and sometimes words) that needed to be assessed, not people’s souls. I would save my conclusions—and I did have conclu-

sions—for the conclusion. And I’m nearing my conclusion now.

I have explained how I tried to operate on the understanding side of the semicolon. But that gives little guidance on when or how to step over to the far side, to render judgment. And in this case, what it overlooks is that, however one assesses justice—however virtue and rights are distributed—power is horribly out of balance in ways that have deeply problematic and deadly results.

Denial and dehumanization, for instance, are in rich supply and are nobody’s monopoly. The number of people I heard dismiss the atrocities committed against Israeli civilians in the October 7 attack and in the subsequent assault on Gaza dismayed me. The same can be said of dehumanization. This is a common phenomenon in wartime, and shrillness is the coin of much public discussion of the Gaza war.

But if denial and dehumanization are widespread, they have not been evenly distributed. The extent to which leading political figures—those in senior positions of authority—in the United States and Israel have resorted to eliminationist rhetoric has no easy parallel.

The tools of political authority are not distributed evenly, nor has been the firepower of those dismissing the death of their adversaries. Those who call for “Palestine from the river to the sea” are denounced in the halls of Congress, often for things they do not mean; those who make similar territorial claims for Israel (and do so in a way that asserts not only the rights of the Israeli state but also the superior rights of the Jewish people, and sometimes are explicitly linked to proposals to forcibly displace Palestinians) are extended invitations.

In Washington DC after October 7, it was unremarkable to claim that each Israeli death on October 7 is equivalent to thirty American deaths because of the relatively smaller population of Israel—and then to measure Palestinian deaths instead against fatalities in Syria or Darfur, varying the scale by which to measure killing in order to minimize or maximize the horror.

It is routine to hold Palestinians responsible for the death toll in their own ranks; to quote official Palestinian figures by noting they come from a government controlled by Hamas but to quote Israeli figures without reference to the exclusionary and supremacist ideology of those ruling the country. Similarly, official Israeli sources have claimed the ability to count accurately every “terrorist” killed, but appear utterly baffled in trying to provide even a rough estimate of the number of civilians killed.

Strident and shrill campus rhetoric against Israel was combatted with legal tools, but calls for continuing the crusades against Muslims or using nuclear weapons on Gaza were barely noticed. A United States government apparatus designed to combat discrimination in education has just been dismantled in nearly all of its aspects except to protect Jews who support the Israeli government—and those same tools are now called upon to target Jews who are critical of Israel.

This uneven distribution of power has shaped the framing of policy discussions and the information that is fed into them. Think tanks began to produce detailed “day after plans” a month into a war, utterly disconnected from the scale of the destruction, the open-ended nature of the Israeli military campaign, and the clear statements of Israeli policy that there would be no day after in the sense pun-

ditions used the term.

I said I would try to speak in paragraphs and I have. But in that last one, I trespassed most of the other boundaries I just claimed to follow—reluctantly, with real misgivings, but also with deep conviction that, in such abnormal times, horrific atrocities and murderous words do have to be labelled as such lest we enable actions we purport merely to understand.

There are many who add that we have an obligation to do so. I do not disagree, but I want to end on a cautionary and practical note.

I find myself very slow to use one word in a previous sentence: “we” –especially when imposing obligations. It is one that I think *we* as scholars need to use carefully. Why? Because I think one contribution we can make is by helping people peer over the border between us and them.

But to speak in a singular voice can be lonely. And to be alone in a dangerous time is dangerous.

This leads me to turn back to Proust for some practicality. I suspect that is the first time that sentence has been uttered in any setting. Writing in Paris in the middle of the First World War, Proust observed, “The surest way of being convinced of the excellence of the cause of one party or the other is actually to be that party.”

Proust was writing during a war that not only caused great bloodshed but also the celebration of that bloodshed. The French and Germans in 1914 mistook their patriotism and moral sensibilities for military capabilities.

Today, even the most compassionate people

seemed for a long time to only muster at best a limp “Yes, but” about the suffering and death of those on the opposite side. So over the past two years, more than a semicolon is needed. “Yes, period.” should be not only a complete sentence but an entire paragraph.

But another paragraph is needed to describe the horrors, the cruelty, and the violence visited at once both blindly and deliberately on the over two million people of Gaza.⁵

And in such a context, those who seek to peer on the other side of a boundary will find themselves exposed. The dangers are real. But my personal experience suggests that there is a reward for crossing to the far side of the semicolon for those who do so slowly.

Public discussions can be polarized, personalized, and characterized by rhetorical inflation. But I have found that makes many (especially non-specialists) hungry for calmer discussions, simply so the din doesn’t drown out their own understanding. Like many colleagues, I have participated in sober and reasoned (if distressed) discussions in classrooms and small groups. I have addressed a Gaza encampment, a synagogue, and mixed audiences; I have spoken with a variety of individuals whose public certainty often obscures private distress.

My experience is that the hunger for informed and thoughtful discussion is great; that speaking softly generally makes it easier for most listeners to hear—and it also makes

it more likely that a cry of conscience, when it does emerge loudly and clearly, seems less like a partisan chant.♦

⁵ Author’s note: In the address I gave in September 2025, I judged Israeli conduct in Gaza in extremely strong terms but did not use the term “genocide.” I have been asked about that since. Was I pulling my punch? Yes, I was. And I have stopped doing so. I do believe the term applies. For the reasons I describe in the address, however, I try not to lead with it when I do use it. I want it to emerge as a conclusion of analysis, not as the premise from which analysis begins. But that is no reason to avoid the term. The point, then, is not to evade the term but to resist a style of argument in which the presence or absence of one word does the work that analysis should do. Those of us in a profession built on peer review should know how easily it can become peer pressure.